

INFLUENCE OF FEEDING FREQUENCY ON GROWTH AND FEED UTILIZATION OF TILAPIA (*Oreochromis niloticus*) FINGERLINGS

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ABSTRACT

A 12-week feeding experiment was conducted to study the effects of varying frequencies on the growth and nutrient utilization performance of Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) fingerlings. *O. niloticus* fingerlings were allotted to four replicated aquaria at the rate of 20 fingerlings per tank. Fish in each treatment tank received diets at 5 percent of their biomass, fed once, twice, thrice and four times daily. A feeding regime of two times per day produced best fish performance in terms of their specific growth rates. Fish weight gain, specific growth rate, protein intake and survival percentage than all other treatments. The rations supplied twice, thrice and four times show significant difference ($P < 0.05$) against once daily feeding frequency. These data suggest that best growth could be achieved when *O. niloticus* fingerlings are fed twice daily in temperate regions.

KEYWORDS: Feeding frequency, feed utilization, Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*), Growth response

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INTRODUCTION

Within the past decades, several studies have been conducted to determine the protein requirements of Tilapia species in the course of advancing the intensification of their culture (Cruz and Landencia, 1977; Mazid *et al.*, 1979; Jauncey, 1982; Falaye and Arogunjo 1989). Nutritionally balanced feeds prepared from good quality feedstuffs and appropriate feeding techniques are important for a successful intensive fish production system. Dupree and Huner (1984) observed that the amounts, texture of fish diets, as well as the feeding frequency affect their acceptability and nutrient utilization by the fish. Consequently, "with the knowledge and development of an effective feeding programme through careful manipulation of the diet formulation and feeding regimes, it would be possible to enhance fish yield under culture conditions.

The present investigation therefore examines the influence of different feeding frequencies on the performance of Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) fingerlings in terms of their growth and nutrient efficiency.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Fish: The fish used for the experimental study were fingerlings of *Oreochromis niloticus* with mean weight, 3.65 ± 0.21 , selected from the Department of Aquaculture and Fisheries, University of Ibadan, fish farm. Satiation feeding level was determined during acclimatization of the fish. At the beginning of the experiment the fingerlings were weighed individually and randomly assigned to four replicated aquaria at the rate of 20 per tank. The stocking rate seems too small?

Experimental procedure: The experimental unit consisted of eight aquaria (37cm x 26cm x 30cm) which was supplied with fresh tap water, supplementary aeration was provided throughout the experimental period by means of 'Rena' model 310 air pumps. A 12 -hour photoperiod was provided by a switch-controlled fluorescent lighting. Adequate water supply was maintained during the feeding trial period.

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Experimental feed: The experimental feed composition used in this study contained 30 percent crude protein in dry matter as shown in Table 1&2. The dietary ingredient were weighed, mixed thoroughly, moistened and compressed through a mincer with 2.0mm die diameter to produce pellets. The pellets were oven dried at 40°C to constant weight and stored in air-tight polythene bags until fed to the experimental fish.

Feeding methods: Fish in each tank were assigned to a feeding frequency of either once, twice, thrice and four times daily at 5 percent of fish biomass. Once daily feeding regime was use as control, while the feeding times were 0900 hours, 1200 hours, 1500 hours and 1800 hours. Each treatment was replicated thrice.

Weekly batch fish weight was determined for each treatment and their daily ration was adjusted based on their biomass accordingly.

Analytical methods: Proximate composition was conducted on replicate samples of the experimental diets and fish before and after the feeding trials as follows: Moisture content was determined by drying samples in oven at 105°C for 24 hours. The crude protein (N x 6.25) was determined using a micro-kjldahi auto-analyzer. Crude lipid content was determined by extraction with petroleum ether (AOAC, 1984). Crude fiber content was estimated by the trichloro-acetic acid method. Ash content was determined by charring sample in a muffle furnace at 450°C for 12 hours.

Statistical analysis: Data on fish growth, food intake, food conversation and dietary protein utilization were subjected to statistical analysis by the one-way analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test and the means were tested for significance (P< 0.05) using Duncan's Multiple Range Test (Duncan, 1955).

The fish growth performances were evaluated as follows:

Mean weight gain = [final mean weight (g) – initial mean weight (g)]

Relative growth rate (RGR) $RGR (\%) = \frac{(W_f - W_i)}{W_i} \times 100$

W_f = final fish weight gain at the end of the experiment.

W_i = initial fish weight at the beginning of the experiment (Fasakin *et al.* (2001)

Specific growth rate (SGR) $SGR (\%/day) = \frac{(\text{Log } W_f - \text{Log } W_i)}{t (\text{days})} \times 100$

Where, $\text{Log } W_f$ = logarithm of the fish final weight gain.
 $\text{Log } W_i$ = logarithm of the fish initial weight.
 t = experimental period in days (Hepher, 1988)

Feed conversion ratio (FCR) $FCR = \frac{\text{feed intake (g)}}{\text{Weight gain (g)}} \text{ (Burel } et al., 2000)$

Gross feed conversion efficiency (GFCE): $GFCE = \frac{1 \times 100}{FCR}$

Protein efficiency ratio (PER) = $\frac{\text{wet body weight gain (g)}}{\text{Crude protein fed}}$

Protein productive value (PPV) = $\frac{(\text{final fish body protein} - \text{initial body protein}) \times 100}{\text{Crude protein intake}}$

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$$\text{Protein intake} = \frac{\text{feed intake} \times \text{percentage protein in diet}}{100}$$

RESULTS

All rations fed were actively consumed by the experimental fish. Apart from treatment 2 with no mortality, all other feeding treatments had a low mortality, and survival was 95%. Fish mortality was not associated with any pathological symptoms. The gross and proximate compositions of the trial diet used for the feeding study are presented in Table 2. Dietary crude protein was 27.66 percent while crude lipid and ash content were 9.14 percent and 14.36 percent respectively. Table 3 shows the growth and nutrient utilization performance of *O. niloticus* during the trial period. At all feeding frequencies tested, the experimental animals exhibited positive weight gains, mean fish weight gains were significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher at increased feeding frequencies. There was a general increase in fish growth above the control treatment, with increased feeding frequency. However, the highest specific growth rate (SGR) (percentage increase in fish biomass per day over the trial period) was recorded at the twice daily feeding. Although the SGR showed slight variation in their values, they were not significantly ($P < 0.05$) different. Both food conversion ratio (FCR) and the Gross Food conversion efficiency of fish improved progressively with increased feeding frequency. The best food conversion efficiency was achieved with fish receiving rations four times daily.

Table 1: Experimental feed formulation

INGREDIENT	COMPOSITION (%)
Fish meal	13.4
Groundnut cake	16.4
Blood meal	8.3
Yellow maize	40.4
Brewer's waste	7.0
Bone meal	1.5
Oyster shell	1.0
Palm oil	6.0
Mineral mix	2.0
Vitamin mix	4.0
Total	100.00

Table 2 : Growth and feed utilization measurement

	TREATMENT			
	1	2	3	4
Initial Mean Weight (g)	3.55	4.0	3.6	3.45
Final Mean Weight (g)	8.15	10.85	9.25	9.10
Mean Weigh Gain (g)	4.60 ^a	6.85 ^b	5.65 ^b	5.65 ^b
Specific Growth Rate (% per day)	1.00	1.20	1.14	1.17
Food Conversion Ratio	4.48 ^a	3.84 ^b	3.76 ^b	3.73 ^b
Gross Feed Conservation Efficiency (%)	22.32	26.04	26.60	26.81
Protein Intake (g)	5.77	7.36	5.96	5.89
Protein efficiency Ratio	0.80 ^b	0.93 ^b	0.95 ^b	0.96 ^b
Productive Protein Value	0.37 ^a	0.26 ^b	0.26 ^b	0.21 ^b
Mortality	5	0	5	5

Figures on the same row having the same superscript are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$)

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Table 3: Initial and final carcass composition of experimental fish (*Oreochromis niloticus*) fingerlings during the study

	TREATMENT				
	Initial	1	2	3	4
Moisture	79.94	73.53	69.32	72.54	72.28
Crude protein	59.10	61.24	61.04	60.63	60.34
Ether	7.90	10.49	14.90	14.41	10.90
Ash	1430	14.40	14.70	15.30	16.50

Treatment 1 was significantly different ($P < 0.05$) in itsr FCR values during this trial. In contrast, protein efficiency depreciated as feeding frequency increased. Tissue protein deposition followed a similar decreasing trend in the fish as frequency of feeding increased. At each feeding time, for the fish, there was significant ($P < 0.05$) effect of feeding frequency effect on protein efficiency ratio. The initial and final carcass composition *O. niloticus* are presented in Table 3.

All fish exhibited an increased in tissue protein over the experimental feeding period. The Productive Protein Values (PPV) of the experimental fish range between 0.21 and 037. There was no significant difference ($P < 0.05$) between the PPV of fish fed twice daily, thrice and those on diet four times daily feeding regime.

Generally, fish placed on the twice daily feeding regime performed best in terms of their weight gains and growth indices (SGR) during this study. This was followed by the group of fish receiving their rations four times daily: but with no statistically significant difference ($P < 0.05$) with regards to specific growth rates

DISCUSSION

From the results, fish survival was high, during the feeding experiment. Fish survival pattern observed in this trial clearly appeared to be unrelated to feeding regimes. Mortality could probably be attributed to handling stress during the experimental period rather than the feeding frequency treatments. The dietary protein levels of feeds in the rations supplied to the experimental fish in this study were similar to those previously reported by Viola and Ariel (1982). Jauncey and Ross (1982) and Falaye and Arogunjo (1989) satisfied the protein requirements of Tilapia for adequate body maintenance and fish growth. Fish feeding and their nutrient utilization vary with size, age and health state of the fish; as diets are more efficiently utilized by younger fish than older individuals.

The food conversation ratio of fish and their growth rate are indices of major importance in determining their culture performance, the FCR values obtained in this trial compared favorably with figures reported for Tilapia (*O. mossambicus*) fingerlings by Cruz and Landencia (1977).

Although the FCR was optimal when fish received their rations four times daily in this trial, the best growth rate (SGR) was achieved as the feeding frequently reduced to twice daily. It might have been possible that more energy was used in ingestion and metabolism of feeds when the whole daily feed was presented to the animals at an increased frequency, thereby leaving a reduced amount of energy for fish growth. It would be noted however that the difference in their SGRs was slight and not statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). At satiation, the feeding of excess dietary energy is not only wasteful but could cause feeding adverse effects fish performance (Henken *et al*, 1986, Ufodike and Akombo 1987). It therefore follows that rations presented to the fish all at once daily resulting to excess energy was not positively utilized for fish growth. Hence at that feeding frequency, food conversation ratio was significant ($P < 0.05$); while the lowest Specific Growth Rate was also recorded during the feeding treatment. Similarly, it is also possible that the observed depression of Protein Efficiency Ratio as well as the tissue protein deposition; with increasing feeding frequency this result to the negative effects of the dearnination and excretion of excess protein.. Similar effects were reported for catfish, *Clarias gairiepinus* by Ufodike and Akombo (Op cit).The FCRs of fish were superior at higher daily feeding frequencies of three and four times while their growth rates were however poorer than the preceding treatment of twice per day feeding. The twice feeding frequency shows highest specific growth rate per day and shows no mortality during this study than other treatments.

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However, any extra advantage at these feeding regimes still needs to be matched against feeding operation costs to determine profitability in subsequent studies. It may be stated from the findings of trial that optimum fish growth of *O. niloticus* fingerlings could be achieved in static water system at a feeding frequency of twice daily, as equally adopted by many commercial fish farmers in Nigeria. At higher feeding frequencies, increased amount of uneaten feed may result in wastage and adverse water pollution problems. It should however be noted that feeding would vary with size and age of the fish. It is worth researching into the cost value, biomass and different climatic influence on feeding regime of *O. niloticus* and to further clarify the effects of other factors on growth response of feeding frequency.

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